

Physicochemical Investigation on Rare Earth Chelates of *o*-(*N*- α -Furfuraldimino)phenolate System

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Manuscript received 23 February 1987, revised 10 December 1987, accepted 24 December 1987

o-(*N*- α -Furfuraldimino)phenol (HFP), and its lanthanon chelates have been synthesised and studied by physicochemical techniques. Irving-Rossotti method has been followed to determine the dissociation constants of the ligand and formation constants of its lanthanon chelates in aqueous medium at different ionic strengths (0.01, 0.05 and 0.1 *M* NaClO₄) and temperatures (25, 35 and 45°). The solid lanthanon chelates have been characterised by molecular mass, elemental analyses, conductance, magnetic, thermal and spectral analyses, and assigned 1:3 (metal-ligand) stoichiometry in which the lanthanon shows nine coordination number. Covalent nature of metal-ligand bond has been found to increase with the increase in atomic number of the central lanthanide ion.

RARE earth chelates of some tridentate Schiff bases have been reported earlier from these laboratories¹⁻³. A perusal of literature reveals that no work has been done so far on the tripositive lanthanon chelates of *o*-(*N*- α -furfuraldimino)phenol (HFP), and hence the same was undertaken for physicochemical investigation and its findings are reported in the present paper.

Experimental

HFP was synthesised by refluxing equimolar ethanolic solutions of *o*-aminophenol and furfural-2-aldehyde, in presence of a drop of piperidine as the catalyst. The brownish yellow precipitate was filtered, washed with water and ethanol and dried in vacuum; quantitative yield of HFP was obtained (m.p. 157°). The solid lanthanon chelates were prepared and characterised by the methods reported earlier^{4,5}. Proton-ligand and metal-ligand constants were determined by potentiometric method according to Irving-Rossotti's technique⁶ at 25, 35 and 45°, ionic strength $\mu=0.1, 0.05$ and 0.01 *M* NaClO₄ in aqueous medium.

Results and Discussion

HFP functioned as a monoprotic ligand. The pK^H values decrease with increasing temperature and ionic strength⁷ in accordance with Debye-Hückel rule. The formation curves attained maxima around $\bar{n}=3$, indicating formation of 1:3 Ln-HFP complexes. As HFP is a tridentate ligand Ln(III) ions assume 9-coordination in these complexes. The refined $\log \beta_3^0$ values⁸ (Table 1) are in the order, Ln < Pr < Nd < Sm < Gd < Tb < Dy < Ho < Er, which is in agreement with the Stagg and Powells

TABLE 1—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR LANTHANON CHELATES OF HFP

M(III) Ion	$\log(\beta_3^0)$			35°	
	25°	35°	45°	ΔH° kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS° JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
La	17.78	17.91	18.03	22.68	416.59
Pr	19.21	19.34	19.43	19.96	435.26
Nd	19.68	19.79	19.87	17.24	434.90
Sm	20.19	20.26	20.39	18.15	446.85
Gd	20.85	20.97	21.08	20.87	469.29
Tb	21.58	21.68	21.76	16.33	468.25
Dy	22.11	22.24	22.35	21.77	496.53
Ho	22.69	22.81	22.90	19.05	498.60
Er	23.21	23.33	23.47	23.59	523.31

pK_{HFP}^H : 8.02 (25°), 7.59 (35°), 7.08 (45°).

rule⁹. $\log \beta_3^0$ values decrease with increasing ionic strength of the medium, in agreement with Hückel equation¹⁰. The stabilities also increase with increasing temperature at a given ionic strength of the medium. Non-linearity of $\log \beta_3^0$ with $-Z^2/r$ for the Ln(III) ions may probably be due to stabilisation arising out of the interaction of 4*f*-orbitals of metal with ligand field¹¹ and increased covalent nature of metal-ligand bonding.

Positive enthalpy values suggest the existence of steric strain around the rare earth metal ions in the chelates, due to fused rings. The positive entropy values suggest favourable chelation.

Solid complexes: Elemental analysis and molecular mass data suggest Ln(FP)₃ stoichiometry for all the lanthanon-HFP complexes (Table 2). The room temperature magnetic moment values of the lanthanon complexes determined by Gouy method, correspond to the formula, $\mu_{\text{eff}} = [2J(J+1)]^{1/2}$ and confirm the tripositive state of the metal in these

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPOUNDS

Compd.	Molecular mass Found/(Calcd.)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		μ_{eff}^* B.M.
		Metal	N	
HFP ^a	178 (187)	—	7.43 (7.49)	—
[La(FP) ₃]	691 (697)	19.83 (19.94)	5.96 (6.03)	Dia.
[Pr(FP) ₃]	694 (699)	20.09 (20.17)	5.93 (6.01)	3.34
[Nd(FP) ₃]	697 (702)	20.40 (20.51)	5.91 (5.98)	3.61
[Sm(FP) ₃]	701 (708)	20.98 (21.19)	5.88 (5.93)	1.57
[Gd(FP) ₃]	709 (715)	21.74 (21.96)	5.83 (5.87)	7.83
[Tb(FP) ₃]	710 (717)	22.05 (22.18)	5.80 (5.86)	9.48
[Dy(FP) ₃]	716 (721)	22.48 (22.61)	5.81 (5.88)	10.43
[Ho(FP) ₃]	717 (723)	22.71 (22.82)	5.74 (5.81)	10.38
[Er(FP) ₃]	720 (725)	22.90 (23.03)	5.72 (5.79)	9.67

*At 308 K. ^aFound/(Calcd.): C, 70.41 (70.59), H, 4.77 (4.81).

complexes. The lanthanum complex was diamagnetic whereas the rest were paramagnetic. The μ_{eff} values also indicate the absence of any metal-metal bonding. Negligibly small conductance values ($6.24-8.55 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) of the compounds suggest them to be non-electrolytes.

Ir spectra: Comparison of the ir spectra of the ligand with those of its lanthanon chelates indicates coordination of the ligand through azomethine nitrogen, phenolic oxygen and oxygen of furfural ring. In case of the ligand (HFP), the band observed at 3465 cm^{-1} corresponds to $\nu_{\text{OH-N}}$ (hydrogen bonded OH). This band disappeared in the lanthanon chelates indicating its deprotonation due to chelation. $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ shift of the phenolic group (1405 cm^{-1}) as obtained towards the higher region ($\sim 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) suggests the bonding between the metal and phenolic oxygen atom. The $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ at 1615 cm^{-1} of HFP shifted to $1590-1605 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes indicating coordination of azomethine group. The new broad bands around 500 cm^{-1} in the ir spectra of the Ln(FP)₃ complexes arise due to M-O stretches. Such bands are also observed in similar

complexes with Schiff bases and oxime suggesting coordinations of furan ring oxygen^{12,13}. The shift in the M-O frequency to higher wave number with increasing atomic number of lanthanide suggests increased covalent character of the metal-ligand bond, the sharp bands at $410-435 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes are assignable to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ vibrations. The absence of ir band around $250-100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, indicates the non-existence of M-M bond¹⁴⁻¹⁶.

The bonding of the ligand FP⁻ in the Ln(FP)₃ complexes may, therefore, be represented as

where, M = Ln(III)

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